

Leadership Structure and Earnings Management in the Quoted Food and Beverages Companies in Nigeria

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾**Owolabi, Sunday Ajao**- Professor of Accounting Department of Accounting, Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria ⁽²⁾**Adegbie, Festus Folajimi**-Associate Professor-Head, the Department of Accounting, Babcock University Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria ⁽³⁾**Aina, Grace Oluwatosin**-PhD Accounting Student-Department of Accounting, Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria

Abstract

Recently, there have been several deliberations on the importance of strong corporate governance; this led to different countries coming up with different guidelines and codes of practice to support governance. This paper investigated the effect of leadership structure on earnings management in selected quoted food and beverages companies in Nigeria. The ex-post facto research design was adopted for the paper. The sample size for this paper was selected from the population based on the number of food and beverages companies that have been consistently trading on the NSE for the period under study (2007-2017). The paper adopted inferential statistics for data analysis. From the findings, the result show that insiders' ownership ($\beta_2 = -0.375$, $t(127) = -3.71$, $p < .01$) and ownership concentration ($\beta_3 = -0.012$, $t(127) = -4.01$, $p < .01$) have significant impact on EM, while CEO duality ($\beta_1 = 0.418$, $t(127) = 6.33$, $p < .01$) reported positive and significant. The findings revealed that leadership structure has a significant effect on earnings management. This paper concludes as insiders' ownership and ownership concentration increases; it leads a decrease in discretionary accruals, i.e., improvement in earnings management practices by companies which do not provide incremental managerial ownership ability to reduce earnings management. This paper recommended that management of this companies are advised to adhere strictly to the code of corporate governance relating to the measures of insider ownership, ownership concentration, and CEO duality as they enhance earnings management practices.

Keywords: Corporate governance, Leadership structure, Earnings management, Managerial ownership

1.0 Introduction

The recent corporate failure in most corporate organizations has led to doubt in the mind of stakeholders on the financial report credibility and reliability, the issue of corporate governance and earnings management has received great attention in almost all sectors of the economy. Owolabi and Dada (2011) said that the corporate world has been facing numerous changes in this ever changing environment, therefore leading to a lot of sudden events taken place in recent times. This frequent change made the corporate world to come out with devices, so as to ensure better performance and consistent growth of the business. This also led to a great increase in the number of laws, rules, and guidelines set in place a heightened standard of corporate governance best practice. According to Ogoye (2002), the increasing number of corporate failures and financial scandals has been caused by incompetence, fraud, and abuse of office by the agents managing the corporations. Earnings management occurs when managers use judgment in financial reporting and in structuring transactions to alter financial reports to either mislead some stakeholders about the underlying economic performance of the company or to influence contractual outcomes that depend on reported accounting numbers (Uadiale, 2012).

Separation of business ownership and control cause the emergence of joint stock companies that allowed millions of people from different locations to own a business jointly. The complexity of businesses across the globe is due to multiple ownership of the business (Miko and Kamardin, 2016). Separation of power and control of private, public companies, shareholders and other investors' supply of information about their companies' performance depend largely on the published financial reports. It is difficult for the shareholders to predict behaviors and actions of managers because managers may falsify the reports of the business activities entrusted to them by the shareholders. This could cause managers to provide misleading information about the assets;

liabilities and risk are taken in the business on the process to earn a profit before the contract ends (Kalbers, 2009).

Hamid, Eddine, Ayedh, and Echchabi, (2014) said that earning management occurs when managers use judgment in financial reporting and in structuring transactions to alter the financial report to either mislead some stakeholders about the underlying economic performance of the company or influence contractual outcomes that depend on reported accounting numbers. Since it is the duty of the management to give account to shareholders, and within the business, stakeholders are included, each stakeholder has his own interest in the business. Therefore each one is having anywhere any authority try to comment on the result of that authority into his own favour. Earnings management is said to be one of the examples which accountant by the will of authorities smoothens their earnings. Ikechukwu (2013),

1.2 Objectives of The Study

The main objective of this study was to evaluate the impact of leadership structure on earnings management in quoted food and beverages companies in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

- i. investigate the effect of insider ownership on earnings management in quoted food and beverages companies in Nigeria.
- ii. examine the linkage between managerial concentration on earnings management in quoted food and beverages companies in Nigeria.
- iii. determine the extent to which CEO duality may influence earnings management in quoted food and beverages companies in Nigeria.

1.3 Research Hypotheses

The following hypothesis was tested:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between insider ownership and earnings management in the quoted food and beverages companies in Nigeria.

H₀₂: managerial concentration has no significant relationship with earnings management in the quoted food and beverages companies in Nigeria.

H₀₃: CEO duality has no significant relationship with earning management in the quoted food and beverages companies in Nigeria.

2.0 Literature review

2.1 Theoretical underpinned

Stewardship Theory

This study was anchored on stewardship theory. Stewardship theory was developed by Donaldson and Davis (1991 & 1993) as a new viewpoint to understand the existing relationship between ownership and management of the company. "A steward protects and maximizes shareholders wealth through firm performance, because, by so doing, the steward's utility functions are maximized" (Cullen, Kirwan and Brennan, 2006 as cited in Ajetunmobi 2016). stewardship theory recognizes the importance of structures that empower the steward and offers maximum autonomy built on trust.

Donaldso (1997) described steward as one who protects and maximizes shareholders wealth through firm performance because by so doing, the steward's utility functions are maximized. More so, stewardship theory de-emphasizes the duality role of Board chair and CEO, suggesting that the unified function empowers the

steward to safeguard the interest of the shareholder. In view of the above, Daly et al. (2003) stressed the fact that for the employees and the executive to protect their reputations they will take those decisions that will improve performance. This is consistent with the position of Owolabi (2011), who argued that stewards are expected to behave rationally because if they refused to take decisions that will improve performance, then the shareholder operating in a free market system can switch to a performing firm and the stewards may lose their job. So in stewardship theory, it is assumed that stewards will act in the best interest of the shareholders (Owolabi, Owolabi & Olanrewaju, 2014).

Stewardship Theory has been framed as the organizational behavior counterweight to rational action theories of management (Donaldson and Davis, 1991 & 1993). The main assumptions underlying the prescriptions of stewardship theory is that behaviors of the managers are aligned with the interest of the principal. Stewardship Theory places greater value on goal convergence among the parties involved in corporate governance than on the agent's self-interest (Van Slyke, 2006). This theory holds that there is no conflict of interests between managers and owners. In stewardship theory, it stresses the top of management as steward whose utility function is maximized when shareholders' wealth are maximized.

Stakeholder's theory

The stakeholder's theory was developed by the Freeman (1984) it is all about identifying the groups who are the stakeholders in a corporation and need to be managed, it assumes that quickest way to destroy a shareholder value is to ignore the stakeholders. Freeman (1984) defines stakeholders as "any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the organization's objectives." According to Miniga (2013) explain that stakeholder theory has become more prominent because of researchers recognize that the activities of a corporate entity impact on the external environment requiring accountability of the organization to a wider audience than simply its shareholders. McDonald and Puxty (1979) proposed that companies are no longer the instrument of shareholders alone but exist within society and, therefore, has responsibilities to that society. Hetherington (1973) critique the shareholder theory that there is no reason to for shareholder to tolerate the corporate, non-profit activity as it appreciably reduces either the dividends or market performance of the stock. Jensen (2001) also critique the shareholder theory for assuming a single valued objective and argue that the performance is of the firm is not measured only by the by gains to its stakeholders.

2.2 Conceptual Framework

Insider Ownership and earnings management

According to Phani, Reddy, Ramachandran, and Bhattacharyya (2016) Insider ownership, as defined in the two ways, the first way is that insider ownership can be defined as managerial ownership, where managers are given ownership rights as a post facto incentive mechanism by owners. The second one is that insider ownership is defined by the de facto ownership rights held by an insider who promotes and also manages (owner-manager). Insider ownership shows various problem encountered by governance which comes as a result of variation in cash flow and the various control rights on ownership.

Ownership Concentration and Earnings Management

Small shareholders would not be interested in monitoring because they would bear all the monitoring costs, but only share a small proportion of the benefit. Consequently, shareholders owning a small fraction of outstanding share have incentives to free-ride in monitoring management. Shleifer and Vishny (1986) suggest that large shareholders have a strong incentive to actively monitor and influence firm management to protect their significant investments (the efficient monitoring hypothesis). Therefore, ownership concentration may reduce agency costs by increasing monitoring and alleviating the free-rider problem (Demsetz & Lehn 1985; Shleifer & Vishny 1986, 1997). Large shareholders are expected to monitor managerial behaviour actions effectively,

which reduce the scope of managerial opportunism to engage in earnings management (Dechow, Sloan & Sweeney 1996). Additionally, there will be less pressure on management to meet short-term earnings expectations because controlling shareholders focus more on the long term. Thus, according to the efficient monitoring hypothesis ownership concentration limit earnings management. Ali *et al.* (2008) and Iturriaga and Hoffmann (2005) find that ownership concentration reduces the managers' discretionary behaviour. However, firms with concentrated ownership may be subject to conflicts of interest between majority and minority shareholders. Large shareholders can exercise their control rights to create private benefits, sometimes expropriating minority shareholders. In fact, controlling shareholders may impose their personal preferences even if those preferences run contrary to those of minority shareholders (Shleifer & Vishny 1997). Therefore, large shareholders may intervene in the firm's management and may encourage managers to engage in earnings management to maximise their private benefits (Jaggi & Tsui 2007).

CEO Duality and Earning Management

CEO duality means the person who is performing the duties of chief executive officer of the firm along the representation in the board of directors. From previous studies, it has been discovered that separating the position of CEO and chairman of the firm enhance the performance of the firm and also help in minimizing agency costs. According to Younis, Hashmi Khalid and Nasir (2016), A CEO duality is a significant board controller. It relates circumstances wherever the firm's CEO plays critical roles as a director of the board. Two challenging has to face on the subject of CEO duality base on the consciousness of whether a firm is a superlative serve by muscular headship (stewardship theory), or by monitoring efficiently (agency theory). The main purpose of this duality is to dish up as a substitute for how much control the chairman own. (Younis, Hashmi Khalid, and Nasir, 2016).

According to Chen and Liu (2010), the term CEO duality occurs when the CEO is also the chairperson of the board of directors. The monitoring mechanism and control mechanism is combined when there is the practice of CEO duality in the firm (Epps & Ismail, 2008). Many kinds of literature discovered that the companies with CEO who also holds the position of chairman tend to engage in earnings management (Sharma, 2004; Chen *et al.*, 2006; Bradbury *et al.*, 2006; Epps& Ismail, 2008; Sarkar *et al.*, 2008; Saleh *et al.*, 2005; Nugroho, 2013).

Earnings Management

For about two decades now earnings management has been an important concept in accounting research. However, different researchers have defined earning management in different words According to (Tanewski and Bartholomeusz, (2006), Earnings management is defined as the process of taking purposeful steps within the limits of Generally Accepted Accounting Principles to bring about the desired level of reported income. Earning management occurs when a manager uses his own personal judgment in financial reporting in shaping business transactions. It also means altering the financial results so as to mislead some stakeholders about the current financial health of the company. Earnings management can be done by changing some accounting practices, restructuring of some certain income and expense, and accruals management.

According to Rafik, (2002), Earnings management practice has gained attraction among regulators, standards setters and accounting profession.in the accouting world, it is not a new accounting world that corporate executive has had secret strategies to mislead the shareholder about the financial statement.

2.3 Empirical review

Spinos (2013) investigated the relationship between managerial ownership and earnings management in times of financial crisis: evidence of the USA. The research employed the modified Jones model on 235 U.S firms listed in the S&P 500 index. The study examines the relationship both in the whole research period (2004-2009) as well as to compare the findings 3 years before (2004-2006) and 3 years after (2007-2009) the economic recession in order to investigate whether the potential association between them is affected by it. The empirical

results provide evidence that during the whole research period there is no significant relationship between managerial ownership and earnings management.

Parveen, Mahmood, and Jan (2016), carried out a study on the impact of ownership structure on earnings management from the Pakistani banking sector. In the study, the ownership structure was divided into two categories: ownership concentration and ownership mix. Banking sector of Pakistan was chosen for this study, and 20 banks were selected. The study period was 2000-2012. Data was collected related to ownership concentration and ownership mix variables. Results showed that independent variables including major shareholders, directors, government and financial institutions negatively affect earnings management of banks. Ownership by local, foreign investors/companies and associated organizations' ownership positively affects earning management of banks.

3.0 Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is the *ex-post facto* research design. The population of this study covered 21 quoted food and beverages companies on the floor of the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE) as at 31st December 2017. In selecting the companies, a non-probabilistic sampling technique of purposive sampling was used to select the quoted food and beverages companies adopted for this study. The sample size for this study was selected from the population based on the number of food and beverages companies that have been consistently trading on the NSE for the period under study (2007-2017), The inferential statistical analyses were adopted, while a panel data regression analysis was employed to analyze the model.

$$EM_{i,t} = \pi_0 + \pi_1 IO_{i,t} + \pi_2 OC_{i,t} + \pi_3 ACEOD_{i,t} + \lambda_1 SIZE_{i,t} + \lambda_2 DEBT_{i,t} + \lambda_3 PERF + v_{i,t} \text{ Where:}$$

EM is earnings management measured by discretionary accruals;

IO = insider/managerial ownership;

OC = ownership concentration,

CEOD = CEO duality;

Control variables

SIZE = firm's size measured by total assets,

DEBT = debt to equity and

PERF = performance measured by earnings per share.

$\pi_0, \pi_{1-3}, \lambda_{1-3}$ = parameters; *i* is surveyed food and beverages companies;

t = time; and

ε = error term.

4.0 Data Analysis

This phase of the study presented the analysis of data collected from the annual reports of listed food and beverages companies in Nigeria on how leadership structure affects earnings in the Nigerian food and beverages companies.

Table 4.1: Panel Results of Leadership Structure and Earning Management

Variables	Dependent Variables: Discretionary Accruals			
	Modified Jones Model	Modified Adapted Jones Model	Lagged model	Forward model
CEO Duality	0.418*** (0.066) [6.33]	0.417*** (0.066) [6.32]	0.124*** (0.031) [3.98]	0.134*** (0.030) [-4.45]
Insider ownership	-0.375*** (0.101) [-3.71]	-0.376*** (0.101) [-3.72]	-0.099* (0.054) [-1.82]	-0.101** (0.052) [-1.95]
Ownership concentration	-0.012*** (0.003) [-4.01]	-0.012*** (0.003) [-4.00]	-0.0028* (0.0015) [-1.85]	-0.0029 (0.0018) [-1.59]
Debt	-0.009 (0.025) [-0.38]	-0.009 (0.025) [-0.38]	-0.0034* (0.0021) [-1.69]	-0.0017 (0.0201) [-0.08]
Size(log)	-0.010 (0.019) [-0.53]	-0.010 (0.019) [-0.52]	-0.018 (0.017) [-1.04]	-0.0195 (0.0167) [-1.16]
Performance	-0.0051*** (0.0017) [-2.91]	-0.005*** (0.002) [-2.93]	-0.0003 (0.002) [-0.16]	-0.0004 (0.0019) [-0.23]
Constant	1.013*** (0.359) [2.82]	1.012*** (0.359) [2.82]	0.544*** (0.0385) [17.8]	0.581** (0.297) [1.96]
Within R-squared	0.4621	0.4631	0.4189	0.4453
F-Statistics	10.49***	10.47***	-	-
Prof.(F-stat)	(0.000)	(0.000)	-	-
Wald Test	-	-	18.38***	14.40**
Prof.(Wald Test)	-	-	(0.000)	(0.034)
Hausman Test	40.17***	40.19***	2.89	2.79
Observations	132	132	132	132
Numbers of Firms	12	12	12	12

Note: Standard errors and t-statistics are in parentheses () and square bracket [] respectively; ***, ** and * represent significance at 1%(2.576), 5%(1.960) and 10%(1.645) respectively.

Source: Author's computation (2019) Extract from STATA output.

Model 2 (Baseline Model-Modified Jones Model):

$$EM_{i,t} = 1.013 - 0.375IO_{i,t} - 0.012OC_{i,t} + 0.418CEOD_{i,t} - 0.010SIZE_{i,t} - 0.009DEBT_{i,t} - 0.0051PERF + v_{i,t}$$

Interpretation

In Table 4.5, the estimated baseline model revealed that the coefficients of insider ownership and ownership concentration are negative and significant at 5% for baseline model (modified Jones model), indicating that they negatively influence discretionary accruals measuring earning management of listed food and beverage industry. Also, the parameter estimate of CEO duality was found to be positive and significant at 5%. It indicates that CEO duality has a positive and significant impact on discretionary accruals used to measure earning management. The signs of all the leadership structure indicators were in tandem with a priori expectation. In magnitude, it shows that a 10% increase in the insider ownership and ownership concentration will deteriorate discretionary accruals measuring earning management by 3.75%, and 0.12% respectively. However, discretionary accruals measuring earning management increases by 4.18% due to a 10% increase in CEO

duality. For the modified adapted Jones model and lagged model measures of discretionary accruals, their parameter estimates are similar to the results of the modified Jones model. The coefficients of modified, adapted Jones model show that discretionary accruals measuring earnings management practices change by 4.17%, -3.76%, and -0.12% due to a 10% increase in CEO duality, insider ownership, and ownership concentration. As for the forward model measures of discretionary accruals, the coefficients of the indicators of leadership structure conform with the parameter estimates under the baseline model, but the coefficients of ownership concentration were not significant at 5% and 10%. The parameter estimates of the lagged model suggest that discretionary accruals changes by 1.24%, -0.99%, and -0.028% due to 10% changes in CEO duality, insider ownership, and ownership concentration, whereas for the forward model, discretionary accruals change by 1.34%, -1.01%, and -0.029% correspondingly.

In regard to the control variables, the parameters of the firm's performance were negative and significant at 5% for the baseline model (modified Jones model). It implies that a firm's performance has a significant impact on discretionary accrual measuring earning management of listed food and beverage firms in Nigeria. However, the coefficient of firm's size was not significant for the four measures of discretionary accruals, indicating that firm's size has no significant impact on discretionary accrual measuring earning management of listed food and beverage firms in Nigeria. For the baseline model, modified adapted Jones model and forward model measures of discretionary accruals, the coefficients of firms' debt is negative and not significant at 5%. Thus, for the baseline model, it suggests a 10% change in firms' debt, size and performance will make discretionary accrual to fall by 0.09%, 0.10%, and 0.051% respectively.

In assessing the overall fitness of the estimated panel regression models, the adjusted within R-squared results on Table 4.5 reveal that with the consideration of leadership structure as a measure of corporate governance along with other firms' factors account for an average 46.2%, 46.31%, 41.89% and 44.53% variation in the modified Jones model, modified adapted Jones model, the lagged model, and forward model of earning management of the selected listed Nigerian food and beverage industry between 2007 and 2017. The overall effects of leadership structure on earning management measured by discretionary accruals were significant at 5% with the results of both F-statistics and Wald test as their probability values are less than 0.05.

Decision: The statistical significance of this model indicates that the study cannot accept the null hypothesis of this model hence the study accepted the alternate hypothesis which says that leadership structure has a significant effect on earning management in the Nigerian food and beverage industry.

5.0 Conclusion and recommendation

This study concluded revealed that insiders' ownership and ownership concentration have a significant impact on earnings management as their coefficients were negative and significant at 5%. It means that as insiders' ownership and ownership concentration increases, it leads a decrease in discretionary accruals, i.e., improvement in earnings management practices by companies which do not provide incremental managerial ownership ability to reduce earnings management. The study recommended that management of this companies are advised to adhere strictly to the code of corporate governance relating to the measures of insider ownership, ownership concentration, and CEO duality as they enhance earnings management practices.

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